

Performing episiotomy nowadays and perineal health complications

Realização da episiotomia nos dias atuais e as complicações à saúde perineal

Realización de episiotomía en la actualidad y complicaciones de salud perineal

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Ana Priscila Franca Correia

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2371-8501>

Faculdade Santa Maria, Brazil

E-mail: francaanapriscula@gmail.com

Vitoria Vilas Boas da Silva Bomfim

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4897-0279>

Centro Universitário Jorge Amado, Brazil

E-mail: pesquisaclinica9@gmail.com

Lucimar de Souza Sampaio

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3575-6257>

Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina, Brazil

E-mail: lssam1@hotmail.com

Vanine Arieta Krebs

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4769-3903>

Hospital das Clínicas de Porto Alegre, Brazil

E-mail: vanineakrebs@hotmail.com

Amanda Fiorenzano Bravo

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5426-3410>

Hospital das Clínicas de Porto Alegre, Brazil

E-mail: afbandrade@hcpa.edu.br

Talita Mendonça Sales

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1944-2928>

Centro Universitário Tiradentes, Brazil

E-mail: talita.flamin@gmail.com

Marcela Rosa da Silva

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1333-1576>

Hospital das Clínicas de Porto Alegre, Brazil

E-mail: marcelasilva@hcpa.edu.br

Lisiane Madalena Treptow

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7677-581X>

Hospital das Clínicas de Porto Alegre, Brazil

E-mail: ltreptow@hcpa.edu.br

Maria Fernanda Bandeira da Silva

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0538-1688>

Universidade Federal de Campina Grande, Brazil

E-mail: Fernanda.bandeira@estudante.ufcg.edu.br

Wilcler Hott Vieira

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4243-8065>

Universidade Federal do Sul da Bahia, Brazil

E-mail: wilcler.hott@gmail.com

Maria Laise dos Santos Pinto

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1214-0938>

Instituto Esperança de Ensino Superior, Brazil

E-mail: mllaise12@gmail.com

Abstract

Pregnancy and childbirth are traditionally female activities that accompany the evolution of humanity. Based on this context, the present study aims to review the risks that episiotomy reflects on women's perineal health. This is an integrative literature review carried out through SciELO, LILACS, BDENF and VHL, through the following DeCS: "episiotomy", "normal childbirth" and "women's health". Combined with each other by the Boolean AND operator. As inclusion criteria: articles available in full, in Portuguese, Spanish and English, that addressed the theme, in the last ten years (2012-2022). As exclusion criteria: articles that did not address the topic and repeated studies in the databases. A total of 689 articles were found, after a combined search of descriptors and operators, 10 articles were selected to compose the final sample, as shown in the table below. Through the information obtained, it can be considered that the episiotomy continues to manifest itself deliberately.

Keywords: Episiotomy; Normal birth; Women's health.

Resumo

A gravidez e o parto são atividades tradicionalmente femininas, que acompanham a evolução da humanidade. Com base nesse contexto, o presente estudo tem como objetivo revisar os riscos que a episiotomia reflete na saúde perineal da mulher. Trata-se de uma revisão integrativa da literatura realizada por meio do SciELO, LILACS, BDNF e BVS, por meio dos seguintes DeCS: “episiotomia”, “parto normal” e “saúde da mulher”. Combinados entre si pelo operador booleano AND. Como critérios de inclusão: artigos disponíveis na íntegra, em português, espanhol e inglês, que abordassem a temática, nos últimos dez anos (2012-2022). Como critérios de exclusão: artigos que não abordassem o tema e estudos repetidos nas bases de dados. Foram encontrados 689 artigos, após a busca combinada dos descritores e operadores booleano, 10 artigos foram selecionados para compor a amostra final, conforme tabela abaixo. Através das informações obtidas, pode-se considerar que a episiotomia continua a se manifestar de forma deliberada.

Palavras-chave: Episiotomia; Parto normal; Saúde da mulher.

Resumen

El embarazo y el parto son actividades tradicionalmente femeninas que acompañan la evolución de la humanidad. A partir de ese contexto, el presente estudio tiene como objetivo revisar los riesgos que la episiotomía refleja en la salud perineal de la mujer. Se trata de una revisión integrativa de la literatura realizada a través de SciELO, LILACS, BDNF y BVS, a través de los siguientes DeCS: “episiotomía”, “parto normal” y “salud de la mujer”. Combinados entre sí por el operador booleano AND. Como criterio de inclusión: artículos disponibles en su totalidad, en portugués, español e inglés, que abordaron el tema, en los últimos diez años (2012-2022). Como criterios de exclusión: artículos que no abordaran el tema y estudios repetidos en las bases de datos. Se encontraron un total de 689 artículos, luego de una búsqueda combinada de descriptores y operadores, se seleccionaron 10 artículos para componer la muestra final, como se muestra en la siguiente tabla. Por la información obtenida se puede considerar que la episiotomía continúa manifestándose de manera deliberada.

Palabras clave: Episiotomía; Parto normal; La salud de la mujer.

1. Introduction

Pregnancy and childbirth are traditionally feminine, herbal activities with exclusive meanings that accompany the evolution of humanity. Pregnancy is surrounded by means of expectations, anxieties, needs of the female and the total family round her, it is the second when all the interest is centered on pregnant women, therefore, the care with her is intense in order to furnish the quality journey possible. to this lady who is generating, in her womb, any other life. Childbirth, on the different hand, is acknowledged as the resolving stage of pregnancy, in which the infant and the whole lot that has fashioned over the closing few months will be born (Carniel et al., 2019; Maciel et al., 2020).

Numerous approaches can happen in girls for the duration of labor and delivery, understanding these probabilities and acquiring records about their symptoms is an increasing number of fundamental so that evidence-based care is utilized in practice, respecting women's rights and favoring the humanization of childbirth. Among the a range of feasible interventions at this time, episiotomy seems (FIOCRUZ, 2020; Aguiar et al., 2020).

Episiotomy is a surgical technique that consists of an incision in the woman's perineum with the intention of growing the lumen of the vaginal introitus to "facilitate" the passage of the fetus thru the vagina. This exercise was once proposed via Ould in 1742 with the purpose of facilitating "difficult" births and grew to become famous in the United States from 1920 onwards, therefore increasing to other international locations turning into a frequent practice. Despite being a surgical practice, this method used to be brought in childbirth care except enough scientific proof of its effectiveness. Even today, specialists proceed to exercise this process with the justification of defending the perineum from disordered lacerations (FEBRASGO, 2018; Santos et al., 2021).

Based on this context, the present study aims to review the risks that episiotomy reflects on women's perineal health.

2. Methodology

This is an integrative literature review carried out through the Scientific Electronic Library Online (SciELO), Latin

American and Caribbean Literature on Health Sciences (LILACS), Nursing Database (BDENF) and Virtual Library of Health (BVS), through the following Health Sciences Descriptors (DeCS): “episiotomy”, “normal childbirth” and “women's health”. Combined with each other by the Boolean AND operator. As inclusion criteria: articles available in full, in Portuguese, Spanish and English, that addressed the theme, in the last ten years (2012-2022). As exclusion criteria: articles that did not cover the topic and studies repeated in the databases (Ercole et al., 2014).

3. Results and Discussion

A total of 689 articles were found, after the combined search of descriptors and boolean operators, 10 articles were selected to compose the final sample, as shown in the table below.

Table 1 - Articles selected to compose the final sample. Brazil. 2022.

Title	Author and Year	Objective	Conclusion
Practice of episiotomy among residents in obstetric nursing	Rocha et al., 2018	To perceive the frequency and justification for performing episiotomy in deliveries attended by way of residents in obstetric nursing.	It used to be evidenced that there was once an episiotomy in 19.7% of deliveries and most of the perineal lacerations occurred. It can additionally be found that the exercise of episiotomy amongst residents is above the advocated by using the WHO, bringing reflections about the education mannequin and the distance between principle and practice.
The episiotomy in the perception of puerperal women	Dengo et al., 2016	To recognize how the parturient used to be knowledgeable and guided about the overall performance of the episiotomy at some stage in childbirth.	There used to be a lack of conversation between fitness specialists and ladies about the technique and about the overall performance of episiotomy, which leads to a misunderstanding about this exercise and the quandary of the woman's proper to pick and autonomy. Thus, there is a want to make bigger understanding and rescue women's autonomy in the manner of childbirth and birth.
Practice of episiotomy in childbirth: challenges for nursing	Pompeu et al., 2017	To pick out the information of postpartum ladies about episiotomy and how this exercise took area at some stage in childbirth.	It used to be observed that girls have little records about episiotomy and it was once mentioned that their lack of know-how about this exercise is a element that contributes to the hobbies overall performance of this system for the duration of herbal childbirth.
Perineal integrity preserved during care provided to parturient women at a referral hospital for women's care	Lima et al., 2017	To describe the perineal integrity preserved at some stage in childbirth care in a referral medical institution in the town of Recife.	It was evidenced that at the moment of the expulsive period of childbirth, the spontaneous relaxation of the maternal perineal structures, the position chosen by the parturient and the conduction of the childbirth in an adequate way, provide the fetal exit in a calmer, less painful and with lower chances. of perineal injuries.
Episiotomy: feelings experienced by postpartum women	Villela et al., 2016	Knowing the emotions and repercussions skilled via postpartum ladies who underwent episiotomy barring prior knowledge.	Complications such as dyspareunia, perineal ache and modifications in perineal recovery have been recognized in girls present process episiotomy. It was once additionally located that perineal pain and dyspareunia are usual postpartum morbidities, and the ladies in this learn about reported, even after a duration of 6 months, perineal pain, adjustments in sensitivity and colour of the perineum region, in addition to partial dehiscence. Therefore, the want for monitoring the female who suffered an episiotomy in childbirth used to be evident, with obstetric violence, as she was once no longer conscious of it.

Episiotomy protocols: effects of the update	Garcia et al., 2019	To examine the occurrence of 0.33 and fourth diploma lacerations between July 2017 and July 2018, for that reason measuring the consequences of the alternate in the standards for the use of episiotomy.	There was once a decrease incidence of extreme perineal trauma, sutures and restoration complications, as measured by using the minimize in the reputation of episiotomy, with a massive exchange in anal sphincter injuries.
Episiotomy: the (un)knowledge of the puerperal woman	Pereira et al., 2021	To describe the know-how of postpartum ladies about the exercise of episiotomy.	It can be located that episiotomy does now not stop lacerations and nevertheless favors the prevalence of third and 4th diploma perineal injuries; in addition to merchandising higher blood loss; dyspareunia; postpartum perineal pain; does no longer forestall accidents to the cephalic pole of the fetus; does now not decrease the chance of urinary incontinence; will increase the danger of postpartum hemorrhage and will increase the chance of infection.
Obstetric violence and its influences on the lives of women who have experienced this reality	Rocha & Grisi, 2017	To analyze the penalties of obstetric violence in the lives of ladies who have skilled this experience.	It used to be viable to look at that ladies go through many needless interventions at some stage in labor, which include episiotomy, inflicting harm to their health. In the reviews of the members of this study, emotions of sadness, anguish, frustration, and impotence had been brought on via the violence that occurred.
Women's sexuality in the puerperium: reflexes of episiotomy	Marambaia et al., 2020	To analyze the perception of postpartum women in relation to the influence of episiotomy on their sexuality.	It was once determined that episiotomy has poor influences on women's sexual health, on account that the intact perineum ensures higher safety all through the sexual act. It is a process that, in addition to no longer stopping injuries, reasons serious troubles for women, such as growing the price of puerperal infection and hemorrhage, contributing to an enlarge in maternal mortality.
Episiotomy and its implications	Peña & Gomes, 2016	Clarify about the warning signs of episiotomy, its effectiveness and repercussions for the woman's life.	It can be viewed that episiotomy need to now not be a movements practice, due to its implications for women's health, sexuality and self-esteem. It is a system that must now not be used in a trivial way, and the girl ought to be knowledgeable and have information about the practice, due to the fact if she does no longer agree and it is performed, it is characterised as obstetric violence.

Source: Authors (2022).

In a find out about carried out via Garrett et al. (2016) with the intention of mapping the perceptions of parturients in relation to the episiotomy and the problems of this method in the postpartum period, they describe that the age of these ladies used to be between 18 and 25 years old, some said fitness troubles at some stage in the duration of pregnancy, namely, gestational diabetes and excessive blood pressure. Still in the equal study, it was once determined that of the 50 female interviewed, there had been a whole of eighty five ordinary deliveries, of which fifty nine have been with the overall performance of episiotomy, and forty five of these tactics had been carried out besides the consent and/or know-how of the parturient (Garret et al. , 2016; Sousa et al., 2022).

Marambaia et al. (2020) demonstrated, thru the interviewees' speeches, the worry of restarting sexual activities, with the overall performance of the episiotomy being the important cause for postponing the return of their sexual activity. The ache

and lack of sensitivity of the perineum additionally highlighted putting elements in the women's statement. These discomforts stated via them at once intervene in the day by day lives of these women, emotions such as disgrace of the manner are bad to existence and the overall performance of every day things to do (Marambaia et al., 2020; Cunha et al., 2019).

The lookup by means of Barros et al. (2018) brings in its scope the significance of humanization for the duration of labor, putting the female as the protagonist, giving her self-confidence and autonomy in the course of labor, respecting her rights and the organic and physiological procedure of parturition, In humanized care the expert will now not operate needless procedures, specifically besides the consent and authorization of the lady (Barros et al., 2018; Grecca et al., 2020).

It is discovered that girls see the overall performance of episiotomy and repetitive vaginal checks as uncomfortable and inhumane (Rodrigues et al, 2018). And that they had been uncovered to the procedures, as in the case of episiotomy besides being knowledgeable beforehand, when they have been wondered why the tactics have been carried out, some said the concept of enlarging the beginning canal, to keep away from dangers to the baby, the dimension of the vagina now not be sufficient for the passage of the fetus and even the incapacity of the woman body. These equal female who went thru comparable conditions noticed their our bodies as faulty (Alves & Cirqueira, 2019).

Episiotomy is characterised through being an act of obstetric violence towards female due to the fact it is frequently carried out barring their consent, thus, the overall performance of this method ends up having a massive affect on the lives of these female due to a violation that can set off trauma ensuing from the terrible trip all through childbirth (Márgda et al, 2017; Nunes et al., 2019).

Solange et al., (2016) highlights the significance of clarification about the manner in question, as it can affect exclusive areas in a woman's life, such as bodily and mental, this takes place due to the lack of conversation between expert and affected person to that ample records be handed on, in a clear and goal way, so that the lady can determine on the episiotomy, due to the fact when accomplished besides the woman's authorization, it is characterized as obstetric violence that can generate irreversible penalties for her (Carniel et al., 2019) .

In this sense, it is fundamental to put together a graph so that there can be academic movements with the motive of imparting empowerment for girls throughout labor, so that they can select the quality alternatives safely and that the gurus worried comprehend how to recognize the choice and giving all psychological aid and humanized assistance. In many cases, there are lacerations of one of a kind tiers that can negatively have an effect on the recuperation procedure and as a result the recuperation of this postpartum lady (Garcia et al, 2019; da Silva et al., 2018).

4. Final Considerations

Through the information obtained, it can be considered that the episiotomy continues to manifest in a activities way and backyard the indicative standards of intervention, inflicting influences such as 1) bodily limitations; 2) limit in self-esteem; 3) challenge in the manner of women's autonomy. Such conditions can be perceived throughout prepartum, transport and postpartum, in view that even in the prepartum and shipping there is no indication or facts for the girl of which positions she can try, which is satisfied for her, limiting the girl to continue to be solely in the lithotomic position, inhibiting their autonomy from their personal physique for the duration of labor and even going in distinction to what says Ordinance No. of the Child (BFHI) that covers as a criterion the practices of Woman-Friendly Care (CAM) making sure that invasive strategies in ladies such as episiotomy should be decreased and, if necessary, it should be justified to the parturient about the need, which differs than what has been considered in chosen studies. In this sense, there is a want for new research to no longer solely instruct experts for a extra humanized care that has their practices based totally on evidence, however additionally to make girls empowered about their our bodies and knowledgeable about their rights, due to the fact solely then will they can also have get admission to to

fitness in its entirety.

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